

Geological mapping of the Kuiper (H06) quadrangle of Mercury

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Kuiper quadrangle (H06) is located at the equatorial zone of Mercury and encompasses the area between longitudes 288°E - 360°E and latitudes 22.5°N - 22.5°S. In this contribution we present the preliminary results of a more detailed geological map (1:3M scale) of the Kuiper quadrangle based on the higher resolution MESSENGER data.

The main basemap used for mapping is the MDIS (Mercury Dual Imaging System) 166 m/pixel BDR (map-projected Basemap reduced Data Record) mosaic. Additional datasets were also taken into account, such as DLR stereo-DEM of the region [1], mosaics with high-incidence illumination from the east and west, and MDIS global color mosaic [2]. The preliminary geological map shows that the western and northern part of quadrangle are characterized by a prevalence of crater materials which were distinguished into three classes based on their degradation degree [3]. Different plain units were also identified and classified as: (i) intercrater, (ii) intermediate, and (iii) smooth plains. Finally, several structures, mainly represented by thrusts, were mapped all over the quadrangle.

Specific targets of interest, detected during the mapping activity, were studied at higher resolution, integrating geomorphologic and spectral analysis.

The geological map will be merged with the adjoining quadrangles and integrated into the global 1:3M geological map of Mercury [4], which is being prepared in support to BepiColombo mission.

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References:

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